

In memoriam Barry Goater 1930–2022

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Barry Goater was born on 14 August 1930 in Southampton. He died in Chandlers Ford on 29 July 2022, aged 92. Barry was educated in Hampshire, taking a BSc in Botany at University College, Southampton. After National Service, he joined the staff of Haberdashers' Aske's Boys' School, Hertfordshire, in 1954 and has been Head of Biology there since 1958. He is a member of the Institute of Biology.

From an early age, he was keenly interested in studying Lepidoptera, as it was a family hobby he shared with his beloved grandfather, who allowed young Barry to accompany him on his butterfly-collecting trips.

His natural history interests are wide. He was one of the most active amateur field lepidopterists in the country, he was also a keen birdwatcher and botanist. He has maintained a close association with his native county and is the author of *The Butterflies & Moths of Hampshire and the Isle of Wight*, which was published in 1974. He is also a co-author of *An Identification Guide to the British Pugs*, published in 1981 by the British Entomological & Natural History Society, as well as a contributing author to Volumes 7, 9 and 10 in the series, *The Moths and Butterflies of Great Britain and Ireland*.

After his early retirement (1988), my colleague Barry extended his interest to European fauna and made frequent collecting trips to the continent. He was a member of the *Societas Europaea Lepidopterologica* and corresponded regularly with European lepidopterists. He travelled to Portugal, Lapland, the Czech Republic, and Bulgaria, but was particularly interested in Spain and France.

He has been a member of several scientific societies: the Botanical Society of the British Isles; the British Bryological Society; the British Entomological & Natural History Society, (Honorary Member and President); the *Societas Europaea Lepidopterologica*, Honorary Member and Vice-President. *Hispano-Luso-American Society of Lepidopterology* (honorary member).

He has been a member of the Editorial Board of the *British Journal of Entomology & Natural History*, *Entomologist's Gazette*, *Entomologist's Record*, *Phegea* (Belgium), *Esperiana* (Germany), *Noctuidae Europaeae* (Denmark), *SHILAP Revista de Lepidopterología* (Spain), *Lepidopterologica Hungarica* (Hungary).

Although he specialised in Macrolepidoptera, he also had considerable experience with the British Pyralidae. He wrote the book *British Pyralidae* at the encouragement of others. He was encouraged in this decision by his friends David Agassiz, Robert Dyke, and Geoffrey Senior, who themselves contributed to the work.

Barry and I have been friends for many decades. His book *British Pyralid Moths. A Guide to Their Identification* was published in 1986. He signed the book and sent it to me in Hungary. The approach of this book was very important for me in the study of the Hungarian Pyralidae species.

Barry and I had a very intense professional correspondence. He was the linguistic proof-reader for many of my English-language studies and several of my books. For all his selfless help, we had a real friendship. Barry wrote the chapter *Evergestinae* in *Microlepidoptera of Eu-*

rope Volume 4. He asked me to draw line drawings of European species. For several years he was a member of the professional boards of *Microlepidoptera.hu* and *Lepidopterologica Hungarica*.

He never complained about his health, but in a letter in early 2022, he complained of increasing fatigue. A few weeks before his death, he was proofreading a long manuscript.

His memory will live with me forever. God rest Barry. *Sit tibi terra levis.*

Some books of Barry Goater's work, the Pyralidae volume are dedicated to me.

List of major publications of which I am aware.

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